

DECam Opens a New Window on the Galactic Bulge

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Project Motivation and Overview

The last decade has seen an era of intensive research on the Galactic bulge spearheaded by large spectroscopic surveys, such as the Bulge Radial Velocity Assay (BRAVA; [1], [2], [3]) and ARGOS [4], along with deep near-IR imaging campaigns such as VVV [5]. However, optical imaging remains an important tool for examining the formation history of the bulge since optical colors are more sensitive to stellar metallicity than the near-IR, and such observations are not as expensive as high-resolution spectroscopy. The modern era has lacked a uniform, deep, multi-band optical survey of the bulge, but the potential scientific return on such an analysis is too great to ignore. Motivated by these considerations, we undertook the Blanco DECam Bulge Survey (BDBS; [6], [7]), named in honor of the scientific contributions of Víctor and Betty Blanco, which is a survey of ~ 200 square degrees of the Southern bulge (Figure 1) using the mainly US Department of Energy (DOE)-funded Dark Energy Camera (DECam) on the Víctor M. Blanco 4m telescope and imaging in its *ugrizY* passbands.

The need for an optical imaging survey is driven by several factors. First, the detection of two red clumps (see, e.g.,

bottom left panel of Figure 2) along various sightlines points toward an X-shaped bulge, which is a feature of bars. Further, there is a strong debate regarding whether the bulge's metallicity distribution, traced primarily through iron abundances, is bimodal or is composed of as many as five different populations. Another point of contention is the bulge's age. Most stars appear to be uniformly old (~ 10 Gyr; e.g., [8], [9]), but spectroscopy of lensed bulge dwarfs argues for a substantial population of young and intermediate-age stars (e.g., [10]). Saha et al. [11] even found evidence for a younger population of massive He-burning stars. A third challenge is the spatial distribution of stars, with Zoccali et al. [12] arguing that metal-poor stars follow a spheroidal distribution while those with higher metallicities than the Sun are concentrated near the Galactic plane. Contributions to the bulge from dissolved globular clusters also remain as an open question (e.g., [13], [14]). BDBS was tailored to address many of these questions, particularly spatial and chemical composition variations traced by *u*-band observations, but accomplishing this task requires processing, calibrating, and dereddening a large data volume.

Data Management Challenges

Comprising 62 science CCDs that span more than 2 degrees on the sky, DECam's large field of view allowed us to cover the > 200-square-degree survey area with 6 filters in only 14 nights of observation. One of the most challenging aspects of the project was the data management and processing needed for the 7000+ DECam exposures, equivalent to > 450,000 individual CCD images and > 3.5 trillion pixels. Our small group was able to solve the data storage and processing problems using the petabyte-scale Data Capacitor II (DC2) high-speed shared storage system, in combination with Carbonate, Indiana University's (IU) large-memory computer cluster, both of which are managed by the Pervasive Technology Institute at IU. The combined computational and storage capabilities of DC2 and Carbonate enabled us to process individual CCD exposures with DAOPHOT [15] in parallel and execute > 2 years of CPU time in just a few weeks. The DC2 system also provided a central location for our geographically dispersed collaborators to interact with the raw and final data products.

The second major technical challenge involved collating the enormous data volume into useful catalogs. The PSF photometry runs produced > 10 billion detections across six passbands of approximately 250 million unique objects on nights with a wide variety of zero points and observing conditions, including a handful of partial and non-photometric nights. For a large fraction of the survey area, we were able to adapt previous high-resolution (1×1 arcminute) near-IR reddening maps from [16] to obtain our final catalog of dereddened *ugrizY* photometry for > 175 million Southern bulge point sources.

Early Science Results and Future Work

One of the most interesting results to come out of BDBS so far is the strong correlation between red clump stellar metallicity and $(u-i)_0$ color (Figure 2). This mapping increases the sample size of red clump stars with accurate metallicity measurements by at least two orders of magnitude when compared with even the largest current spectroscopic surveys. In contrast with many previous results, we find that a large

Figure 2. The correlation between $(u-i)_0$ and red clump metallicity as measured via spectroscopy (left) along with the derived metallicity distribution functions summed across lines of constant Galactic latitude (right). The gray histograms are the BDBS results, while the red histograms are for the smaller-sample spectroscopic results from [12]. Note that the $b = -4$ degree field does not show any evidence of bimodality, but a secondary metal-poor component (cyan lines) seems required to explain the outer bulge distributions. (From [6], with permission)

fraction of the bulge mass, particularly at lower latitudes, follows a unimodal metallicity distribution with a long tail that is reminiscent of one-zone closed-box enrichment models (e.g., [17]), rather than a bimodal distribution. The result suggests that a large fraction of the bulge's mass formed during a single high-intensity star formation event < 1 Gyr, and not through multiple short bursts.

Interestingly, Figure 2 does show that fields exterior to $b \sim -6$ degrees appear bimodal. However, if the underlying metal-rich peak represents the same distribution as the unimodal population observed for interior fields, the contribution of the metal-poor component is significantly reduced compared to previous estimates (e.g., [12]), in some cases by more than 50%. The origin of the metal-poor component is not understood, but future work will investigate this problem by leveraging photometric BDBS metallicities with *Gaia* proper motions to produce 3D chemodynamical maps for millions of red clump stars.

Our survey footprint spans an area large enough to include the complete tidal radii of 26 globular clusters, all with $\sim 1''$ image quality, and our catalogs frequently reach near or below the main sequence turnoff. The mysterious object FSR1758 was advanced as a possible new dwarf galaxy, but BDBS reveals it to be an interesting metal-poor globular cluster in the bulge without any obvious tidal structure (Figure 3).

A full data release of the BDBS data to the community is contemplated for late 2021. As Rubin Observatory sees first light, it will become possible to use the BDBS survey as a first-epoch astrometric dataset, potentially with Rubin/LSST imaging pushing precise astrometry (and bulge/disk separation) to $g = 22$ or fainter (3 mag past *Gaia*) and perhaps providing a definitive answer to the question of whether a significant number of intermediate age stars lurk in the bulge. The BDBS survey also provides a glimpse of what is to come when Rubin Observatory images the Milky Way.

Figure 3. The top left panel shows the BDBS density map within several degrees of FSR 1758 with two nearby, but unrelated, globular clusters highlighted in cyan. The top middle panel shows a *Gaia* vector point diagram with the cluster members indicated by the large red circle. A BDBS CMD is shown in the top right panel for an area within 10' of the cluster center (gray points are all data; black points are proper motion members). The bottom left map shows the integrated orbit (purple) and potential member stars identified by BDBS (cyan) and Barbá et al. [19] (blue). Note that previous claims of tidal structure, such as the clump of blue stars near $(l,b) \sim (-10.5, -4.5)$, appear to be related to an over-density of background stars that happen to have a comparable proper motion to the cluster. (From [6], with permission)

The authors acknowledge support from grant NSF AST-1413755.

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